

Domestic Migrant Workers in Kerala and their Socio Economic Condition

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S.Arya

Research Scholar, University of Kerala, TVM

Abstract

Recent years, labour from central India and north eastern states of the country have been moving to Kerala expecting better employment opportunities, wages, living condition. Now, they become the prime labour source of our state. This study is focussed on socio-economic characteristics of domestic migrant labours, being power engines of Kerala economy. In the last few decades, they had made significant influence and impacts in the economy and social fabrics of the Kerala state.

Keywords: Migrant Labours, Employment, Wage.

Inflow of domestic migrant labours expecting better wages and social environment have become the power engines moves in Kerala Economy. The vacuum created by semiskilled and unskilled workers in our social strata due to the migration to middle east and other countries, were bridged by workers from north and north-eastern states. The boom in construction sector due to the inflow of money into our state, demanded semiskilled and unskilled labours attracted workers from various part of our nation.

The current influx of DML is got strengthen after 1990s, which is different from easter years in terms of occupation, mobility and settlement. The migrant labours spreaded all over Kerala and engaged in sectors like constructions, hotels, restaurants, brick kilns, bakeries, tailoring shops, jewellery and in all most all of manufacturing industries. They have replaced local workers in most of the sectors and it has been estimated that, more than 25 lakhs of DMLs are working in Kerala and 2.3 lakhs young Turks have been arriving here every year for fulfilling the demand of the state economy.

Some attempts were made by some scholars to study this area with different perspectives. The major studies on migrant labours in Kerala were done by Dr V Prakash (2012) and by Liji K T (2016). In their study on Domestic migrant labours in Kerala (2013), GIFT had made an attempt to enumerate migrates and made a reasonable estimate of DMC in Kerala. The present study is an attempt to highlight and subsume certain areas that not highlighted in the past studies. This study is based on secondary data published by the Gulathi Institute of Finance and Taxation.

Objectives

- To analyse distribution of DML by state of origin and age wise in Kerala.
- To sort out distribution of DML by occupation, sector of employment and wage rate.
- To look into the socio economic characteristics of DML.

Migrant Labours and Kerala Society

Kerala state has been experiencing large inflow of migrant labours from far away states for the last one decade. In initial days, the migrants were from the neighbouring state of Tamil Nadu and that mostly characterised as seasonal migrants for short-duration. Nowadays the state has witnessed the flow of migrants from far distant states like Bihar, Assam, Bengal, Orissa, UP etc. Growth in our higher education sector that more and more engineering colleges, poly technique, arts and science colleges, community colleges, ITI, etc has changed the attitude of our society, parents and student community. Now, jobs available in our primary and secondary sectors, where hard working labour force are needed don't attract our youngsters due to social stigma, social status and allergy to blue colour job.

Analysis

1. States of Origin and Age Distribution of DML in Kerala.

The state has migrant labours from all the parts of nation. They hail from West Bengal(20%) in largest proportion and also from other states like Bihar (18.10%), Assam(17.28%), Uttar Pradesh(14.83%), Orissa(6.67%) etc(see table 1). Almost all of the workers from other states are males and belong to the age group in between 24-36 and about 90.89% are in the age group below 36years. Very few number are above the age of 36 years which is 8.03% and below age of 12 years i.e. 1.09%. They flex their muscles in their prime age for building and reconstructing Kerala Economy.

Table 1 Distribution (%) of DML by State of Origin

State	Age Class in Years						Percentage
	Below 18	18-23	24-29	30-35	36 and above	not reported	
U P	00	38.53	38.53	15.60	7.34	0	14.83
ASSAM	1.57	50.39	34.65	10.24	2.36	0.79	17.28
West Bengal	1.36	46.26	29.25	14.97	7.48	0.68	20.00
Bihar	0.75	34.59	33.08	21.25	9.03	1.50	18.10
Orissa	2.04	34.69	30.61	20.41	10.20	2.04	6.67
Others	1.18	37.65	37.65	14.71	8.82	0	23.13
Total	1.09	40.95	34.29	15.65	7.32	0.68	100

Source: Report submitted to Labour and Rehabilitation Department, by GIFT, Government of Kerala- Feb 2013.

2. Distribution (%) of DML by Occupation and Sector of Employment

The noticeable facts of DML in Kerala is that they have occupied in all unskilled and skilled sectors of the economy. They are largely concentrated in booming construction sector i.e. about 60%. It is estimated that unskilled labour is the largest group of DML and the next category is that of semi skilled workers, working in construction sector, manufacturing sector, hotels, restaurants, they have also being working in flooring, carpentry and electrical works too. DML have also occupied our agriculture sector deserted by our people, who had migrated to other countries seeking better salary and social status. Now, the Kerala Economy is driven by the largely by DML. The data are shown in table 2.

Table 2 Sectors of Employment

Occupation	Sector of Employment							Total
	Agriculture	Construction	Hotel and Restaurant	Manufacturing	Trade	Others	Not reported	
Carpenter	-	0.54	-	0.14	0.14	0.81	0.14	1.90
Electrician	-	-	0.14	-	-	0.14	0.14	0.68
Mason/Flooring	-	3.54-	-	-	-	-	0.14	3.68
Sales Person	0.14	0.27	0.14	-	0.14	-	-	0.68
Tailoring	-	-	-	0.14	-	0.27	-	0.41
Skilled Work	0.14	10.61	0.54	3.13	0.14	3.67	0.27	18.50
Unskilled Work	2.04	43.40	5.44	4.22	1.36	11.56	1.50	69.52
Others	--	4.91	0.54	0.67	-	0.15	-	2.45
not reported	-	0.27	0.14	0.14	-	0.68	0.95	2.18
Total	2.31	60.00	6.94	8.30	1.77	17.55	3.13	100

Source: Report submitted to Labour and Rehabilitation Department , by GIFT, Government of Kerala- Feb 2013

3. Distribution (%) of DML by Daily wage

The average daily wage earned by the DML is in between ₹300 and ₹500 per day. About one third of them get the wage of ₹400 per day, another one third gets between ₹300 and ₹400 and the rest get only below ₹300. The wage earned by a DML does not depend on whether they work under contract or as a casual labour. The details given in table 3.

Table 3: Wages Earned By DML

Wages Per Day (Rs)	Percentage of Labour Reporting
Not Reported	2.45
Below 300	29.12
300-399	35.51
400-499	23.13
500 & above	9.80
Total	100

Source: Report submitted to Labour and Rehabilitation Department, by GIFT, Government of Kerala- Feb 2013

Conclusion

The objective of this paper is to analyse certain socio economic characteristics of migrant workers in Kerala. The major share of skilled and unskilled domestic workers are youngsters belonging to the age group of 18 to 35 years. The major reasons behind the migration of these labours is the low wage rate and lack of sufficient employment opportunities in their native place , but at the same time high wage rate, availability of abundant job opportunity and better living conditions are their attractions in the Kerala. But the nature and strategy of these workers are still remain as same. Most of them are employed in menial sector deserted by native workers and working under informal contracts without any social security or agreements. So they does not come under the preview of judicial scrutiny.

The skill level of migrants has not improved even after migration. Almost all of them engaged in various menial sectors like construction, brick kilns, agriculture etc and about 60% of them are in unskilled areas.

Always they get relatively low wages compared to native workers where migrants get only average wage of Rs 400 per day, the natives get an average of Rs 700 per day. The living condition of migratory labours in their work site is pathetic crowded in small room without any sanitation provision. Their shelter don't have sufficient space, toilets and not better than cowshed. They are actually breeding centres of contagious diseases. Their mental and physical strength are weekend day by day due to pathetic living condition nature of job and rough handling of employers. So, social, health and police departments can do some extensive activities among DML in collaboration with other state government and NGOs to mitigate their mental and physical trauma by providing healthy accommodation and medical care.

Recommendations

- Local self offices can put forward a system of legal registration of migrant workers and providing labour cards with a unique identification number.
- Take measures to Provide proportionate wages to the migrant labours according to native workers. Labour unions must take up the grievances of DML at political and Government forums and make sure that they are addressed properly
- Inclusion of labour welfare schemes in the state budget.
- Starting programmes to provide skill development training for young migrant labours.
- Ensure work safety and insurance programme for DML.
- Initiating help hands for the DML in collaboration with NGOs ang native governments of migrant labours.

Now, the number of migrant labours is well beyond the acceptable limit. So initiatives for introducing better migratory policy are necessary to keep up a healthy sustainable society. The State of Kerala , which is one of the most democratic and developed region of India, is responsible to provide healthy- environment, to the migrant labours because they are the development engines of Kerala.

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